

both seasons, except with 150 kg N/ha as PU and 120 kg N/ha as NECU in 1988 (see table). NECU at 90 and 120 kg N/ha gave yields similar to those of PU at 120 and 150 kg N/ha.

The superiority of NECU to PU is also shown by the quadratic response functions:

$$\text{for PU, } Y = 3543 + 18N - 0.011N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99;$$

$$\text{for NECU, } Y = 3556 + 31N - 0.056N^2,$$

$$R^2 = 0.99,$$

where Y is yield in kg/ha.

The correlation ($r = 0.98^{**}$) between productive tillers and average grain yield was significant and positive. ■

Integrated pest management – diseases

Outbreak of leaf and neck blast in boro rice crop in Bangladesh

A. K. M. Shahjahan, H. U. Ahmed, M. A. T. Mia, M. A. Hossain, N. R. Sharma, and N. S. Nahar, Bangladesh Rice Research Institute, Gazipur, Bangladesh

Epidemics of blast caused by *Pyricularia grisea* have been recurring in Bangladesh every 3 or 4 yr. In the 1990 dry season (boro) crop, leaf (LBI) and neck blast (NBI) on both local and modem cultivars were higher in some locations than they had been the previous 2 yr. NBI incidence during rice crop maturity (Mar-Apr 1990) was so severe, we surveyed outbreaks in different regions.

Disease incidence (%) was assessed in 25-35 fields/region by counting the number of infected and healthy tillers or panicles of 3 × 3 hills in 9 sampling spots taken in a diagonal direction per field. Severity was rated on a 0-9 scale. The cultivars grown and prevailing tempera-

ture, humidity, and rainfall also were recorded.

The outbreak covered an average 45% of the area planted to boro rice, although its intensity varied across locations. Incidence and severity were higher in the northeastern part of the country than in the northern and southwestern parts. Disease occurred on crops growing on all types of land and soil types (see table). In region I, plots with severe NBI were also affected by low temperature.

During Jan-Mar 1990, humidity was higher at 0600 h and 1200 h, and the difference between maximum and minimum temperature was less than in 1989 (see figure). The high humidity was unusual, and frequent but light rainfall during the period kept rice leaves wet for longer periods in the morning. This favored blast development.

The cultivars grown in the different regions had not changed during the last few years. The reason for the 1990 blast outbreak appears to be related to weather. ■

Incidence and severity of leaf and neck blast in 1990 dry season crops in some regions of Bangladesh.

Region ^a	Area planted (x10 ³ ha)	Fields examined (no.)	Area infected (%)	Land type	Soil type	Incidence (%)		Severity (0-9)	
						LB1	NB1	LB1	NB1
I	179	28	22.8	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	10-100	5-9	3-9
II	605	35	94.1	Low medium high	Sandy loam to clay loam	3-50	1-20	3-9	2-5
III	339	25	4.5	Low medium	Clay loam	1-85	1-75	2-9	5-9
IV	215	34	19.4	Low medium	Sandy loam	2-10	1-30	1-3	1-2
V	139	27	50.0	Low medium high	Clay loam to clay	5-100	5-50	4-9	1-3
All	1477	149	44.7	Low-high	Sandy loam to clay	1-100	1-100	1-9	1-9

^a I = Greater Dhaka district, II = Greater Tangail and Mymensingh districts, III = Greater Sylhet district, IV = Greater Rangpur and Dinjpur districts, V = Greater Khulna and Jessore districts. Cultivars grown: I = BR1, BR2, BR11, BR14, IR8, Pajam, and locals; II = BR1, IR8, BR14, Pajam, Purbachi, and locals; III = BR3, BR14, BR17, BR18, IR8, Pajam, and locals; IV = BR9, BR14, and locals; V = IR50, Purbachi, Ratna, and locals.

Prevailing relative humidity (RH), temperature, and number of rainy days, Jan-Mar 1989 and 1990.

Effect of plant extracts in controlling rice tungro

C. Selvaraj and P. Narayanasamy, Department of Plant Pathology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

We screened 32 plant species belonging to 23 families for their ability to control tungro (see list).

Extracts were prepared by grinding plant tissues with sterile water, at 1 ml water/g of tissue, in a mortar and pestle. The macerate was expressed through cotton wool and diluted by adding sterile water to 10% concentration (wt/vol). Detergent was added at 1 ml/liter of extract and the mixture sprayed on 15-d-old ADT31 rice seedlings.

Seedlings were inoculated with viruliferous green leafhoppers *Nephotettix*

virescens Dist. at 2 insects per plant 24 h after spraying. Control plants were sprayed with 0.1% detergent solution alone. Two replications of 10 plants each were maintained for each treatment. Number of plants infected and incubation period were recorded.

All plant extracts tested reduced tungro infection. Seed extract of *T. terrestris* was most effective in reducing tungro infection, followed by leaf extracts of *V. negundo* var. *purpurascens*, *Catharanthus roseus*, and *Aloe vera*, and stem extract of *Cissus quadrangularis* (see table). The same extracts significantly prolonged incubation. Plants whose extracts were tested for tungro control:

Andrographis paniculata (Burm.f) Wall ex Nees.

Agave americana Linn.

Catharanthus roseus (L.) G. Don.

Cascabela thevetia (L.) Lippold.

Effect of some plant extracts on tungro infection in rice.^a

Source of extract	Reduction (%) of infection over control	Incubation period (d)
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	45 (42.13) a	12.6 a
<i>Vitex negundo purpurascens</i>	41 (39.82) a	12.4 a
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i>	34 (35.70) b	12.2 a
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	34 (35.67) b	12.1 a
<i>Aloe vera</i>	34 (35.68) b	11.8 a
Control	0 (0.99) c	10.4 b
LSD (P = 0.10)	3	0.8

^a Figures in parentheses are arc sine transformed values. In a column, figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

Calotropis gigantea (L.) R. Br.

Tridax procumbens Linn.

Cylindropuntia ramosissima (Engler) Kunth.

Cassia auriculata Linn.

Carica papaya Linn.

Cleome gynandra Linn.

Parthenium hysterophorus Linn.

Ipomoea staphylinia Roem and Schultus.

Ipomoea carnea Jacq.

Croton bonplandianum Bail.

Euphorbia tirucalli Linn.

Jatropha glandulifera Roxb.

Pedilanthus tithymaloides (L.) Poier.

Synadenium grandii Hook.

Ocimum tenuiflorum Linn.

Aloe vera Linn.

Urginea indica Kunth.

Ficus racemosa Linn.

Ficus benghalensis Linn. var. *benghalensis* King.

Acacia nilotica (L) Willd. ex. Del. subsp. *indica* (Benth) Brepan.

Areca catechu Linn.

Antigonon leptopus Hook & Arn.

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb.

Datura metal Linn.

Vitex negundo Linn. *negundo*.

Vitex negundo var. *purpurascens* Sivaranjan & Mold.

Cissus quadrangularis Linn.

Tribulus terrestris Linn. ■

Optimal stage to apply Rabcide 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide for rice blast (BI) control

M. I. Ahmed and T. Raza, *Plant Pathology Department, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan*

We studied the optimum stages for treating rice with Rabcide (4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide), an organophosphorus pesticide, in 1989 and 1990.

Basmati 385 was transplanted at 31 d after seeding in 2- x 4-m plots. Nine treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. *Pyricularia grisea* (= *P.*

oryzae) was inoculated at 10, 20, 30, and 40 d after transplanting. Rabcide was applied at 0.5 g/8 m².

Grain yield was highest with spraying at early and late booting and after flowering, and at primary infection (see table). Yield was lowest with no treatment and with one spraying after flowering. Neck BI was lowest when the crop was sprayed three times and highest with only one spraying at early booting. Results indicate a direct relationship between disease incidence and yield.

One application of Rabcide, at primary infection, controlled BI adequately. Three applications gave the highest yield, but took three times as much chemical and labor.

Grain yield and broken necks of rice following Rabcide application against rice blast.^a

Spraying schedule	Grain yield (kg/100 plants)		Neck blast/100 Panicles in 1990
	1989	1990	
At primary infection	1.9	1.9	2.5
At early booting	1.6	1.6	9.5
At late booting	1.6	1.6	4.2
After flowering	1.5	1.4	7.2
At early booting and after flowering	1.8	1.7	3.2
At early booting and late flowering	1.6	1.6	4.2
At late booting and after flowering	1.6	1.6	4.2
At early and late booting and after flowering	2.0	2.1	1.5
No spray	1.2	1.2	17.0

^a Each figure is a mean of 4 counts.

Integrated pest management – insects

Life history of two braconid parasitoids of rice leaffolder (LF) in the laboratory

Guo Yu-jie, K. L. Heong, and R. P. Basilio, *IRRI*

Two braconids, *Cardiochiles philippinensis* (Fig. 1a) and *Macrocentrus philippinensis* (Fig. 1b), are the dominant parasitoids of LF larvae in the Philippines. We studied their life history under 26 ± 3°C temperature and 75 ± 10% relative humidity.

Newly emerged parasitoid adults were paired and placed in an oviposition cage (23 cm in diameter x 60 cm high) with 20 3d-instar larvae of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on potted plants. Host larvae were replaced daily until the parasitoid died.

Parasitized larvae were reared on potted rice plants for 7 d, then transferred individually into test tubes (16 mm in diameter x 150 mm high). Fresh rice leaves were provided every other day